

ANALYSIS OF THE DYNAMICS OF QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS OF THE NUMBER OF RODENTS AND THEIR ECTOPARASITES IN THE TERRITORY OF KYZYL KUM AND USTYURT IN THE MODERN PERIOD

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Abstract. *The analysis was carried out using archival epizootological data from the anti-plague institutions of the Karakalpak branch of the Republican Center for Plague Prevention (RCPPRK) of the Committee for Sanitary and Epidemiological Welfare and Public Health of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan during the period of seasonal and year-round observations of biotopes from 2016 to 2024 [2]. The survey of the territory controlled by the RCPPRK was carried out on the basis of and in accordance with the annual Work Plans of the above-mentioned anti-plague institutions, approved by the Director of the Republican Center for Plague Prevention of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *landscape-epidemic regions, vicinity, representatives of mammals, population growth.*

Introduction

Surveys of the Kyzylkum and Ustyurt Deserts were conducted in sectors corresponding to tactically verified criteria for epidemic and epizootic indicators, generally accepted in the preventive anti-epidemic activities of anti-plague institutions [3-5]. In the Kyzylkum Desert, the biogeocenoses of the landscape-epidemic regions of the Aral Sea Sands, Akchadarya, Beltau tract, Central and Western Kyzylkum, and Nukus Sands were studied, covering a total area of 3,622,000 hectares. In the Ustyurt Desert, the South Ustyurt and post-aquatic sands, the flat part, and the vicinity of Barsakelmes were studied, covering a total area of 1,098,000 hectares.

Surveys were organized primarily during the spring-summer and autumn-winter seasons, from the third ten-day period of February to the third ten-day period of November, depending on planned objectives and the practical need to adjust the timing of fieldwork within the framework of survey tactics [2, 3]. Thus, the territories of the Kyzylkum and Ustyurt natural autonomous plague foci were surveyed. Depending on the epizootic situation, between 193 and 654 sectors of the primary districts were surveyed, an average of 357 sectors in the Kyzylkum Desert, and between 70 and 152 sectors of the primary districts, an average of 10 sectors, in the Ustyurt and Aralkum natural foci. In this case, in total, during the analyzed modern period, 64,680

Fig. 3. Abs. ratio of the most frequently encountered species in catches to the total number of rodents captured.

Thus, the great gerbil – *Rombomys opimus* Licht. – continues to be the main host species in the Kyzylkum and Ustyurt natural plague foci [6, 7].

During the analyzed period, the host species abundance in the analyzed part of the Kyzylkum LED varied from 0.2 to 5.6 animals per hectare, with a downward trend in abundance and number of animals in catches observed in all survey sites (Fig. 3).

It is worth noting a similar negative trend in the overwhelming majority of the survey area, using the example of the percentage of young individuals of *Rombomys opimus* to the total number of captured rodents in the spring survey period, including in the autumn period, with the exception of the surveyed areas of the Ustyurt territory, where positive dynamics in this indicator were noted (Fig. 4).

It should be noted that the periods of most active generation vary across the survey sites. While in the Kyzylkum region in spring, the periods of highest quantitative catches were recorded from the first and second ten-day periods of April to the first and second ten-day periods of June, in autumn this period is represented by the period from the first ten-day period of September to the third ten-day period of October to the first ten-day period of November. Moreover, 2024 differs from the median observations in that in autumn, intensive population growth was observed from

the second ten-day period of August to the second ten-day period of November. In the territory of the Ustyurt sands, the initiation of the spring active generation of the hostal species varies from the 2nd decade of February to the 3rd decade of April, where the end of the active phase coincides with the periods from the 2nd decade of May to the 3rd decade of July, the autumn period is distinguished by greater stability of the sampling dates and is variable from the 1st, 2nd decade of September to the 3rd decade of October, while 2024 is distinguished by an earlier activation of the generative process, namely from the 1st decade of August, which, in the overall understanding of the process, indicates active transformational and adaptive natural phenomena in the territory of the Aral Sea regression.

Considering the per-species indices of occurrence from the entire set of the considered rodent species in the studied period in these territories, then, firstly, undoubtedly, the most common families include gerbils (*Gerbillinae*), which made up a total of 91.71% of dominance, jerboas (*Dipodidae*) - 1.13% and squirrels (*Sciuridae*), namely the genus *Spermophilus* - 1.09%. It is also worth noting the prevalence of the species *Mus musculus* in catches, which amounted to 5.54%. The distribution of the prevailing statistically significant indices of occurrence in terms of the degree of hostility among these species was, in descending frequency of intraspecific occurrence, the following ratio - among *Gerbillinae*: *Rhombomys opimus*; *Meriones meridianus*; *Meriones erythrorurus*; among *Dipodidae*: *Allactaga elater*; *Dipus Sagitta*; *Allactaga major*; and among *Spermophilus*: *Spermophilus fulvus*; *Spermophilopsis leptodactylus*. The presented data allow us to demonstrate a complete acceptance relationship with the data of previous studies on hostility indicators and fidelity and dominance indices [6-8].

Examining the annual quantitative occurrence of various rodent species in catches in the desert landscapes of the Kyzylkum and Ustyurt deserts, the following is noted: on average, 15 species are caught annually, with no significant decrease. The least frequently encountered species include representatives of the *Dipodidae* family—*Allactaga severtzovi*, *Pygeretmus platyurus*, *Eremodipus lichtensteini*—as well as *Microtus arvalis*, *Ellobius talpinus*, and *Nesokia indica*. *Eremodipus lichtensteini* and *Diplomesodon pulchellum* have not been encountered for the longest time.

The following data on ectoparasites were obtained during the analysis. The most dominant genus of fleas in the collections both in the Kyzylkum territory and in Ustyurt were fleas of the genus *Xenopsylla*, whose share of the total indicators was 81.6% and 70.1%, respectively. The

next most prevalent were fleas of the subgenus *Nosopsyllus*, which territorially accounted for 12.02% in Kyzylkum and 21.2% in Ustyurt. The next most prevalent genera in the biotopes of Kyzylkum were the genera *Coptopsylla* - 5.03% and *Stenoponia* - 0.7%; in the landscapes of the Ustyurt territory, the ratio was represented by the genera *Coptopsylla* - 8.2%, *Mesopsylla* - 5.09% and *Stenoponia* - 2%. Thus, the vectorial prevalence indicators for the given observation period in the Kyzylkum Desert correspond to fleas of the genus *Xenopsylla*, subgenus *Nosopsyllus*, and genera *Coptopsylla* and *Stenoponia*. The vectorial prevalence indicators for the Ustyurt landscapes, in descending order of prevalence, correspond to fleas of the genus *Xenopsylla*, subgenus *Nosopsyllus*, and genera *Coptopsylla*, *Mesopsylla*, and *Stenoponia*.

Fig. 5. Ratio of rodent occurrence indices.

The results of the analysis of occurrence indices by significance level (≥ 1) are presented below in the data for the studied areas of the deserts of Uzbekistan. In the Kyzylkum territory, the dominant *Xenopsylla* flea species is mainly represented by *Xenopsylla hirtipes* – with an occurrence index of 61.55%, followed by *Xenopsylla gerbilli* – 32%, and *Xenopsylla conformis* – 6.2%. Among fleas of the subgenus *Nosopsyllus*, *Nosopsyllus tersus* is dominant – 75%, while *Nosopsyllus turkmenicus* is less represented – 24.3%. Among the fleas of the genus *Coptopsylla*, the most numerous is the subgenus *Coptopsylla lamellifer* - 94.6%, significantly less - 4.6% are present *Coptopsylla bairamaliensis*; fleas of the genus *Stenoponia* are represented exclusively by the subgenus *Stenoponia vlasovi*.

The flea landscape of the Ustyurt territory is more diverse and differs from the indicators of the Kyzylkum territory, where the indices of occurrence according to the degree of prevalence were distributed in the following order: the dominant *Xenopsylla* is mainly represented by *Xenopsylla skrjabini* - the index of occurrence is 65.1%, followed by *Xenopsylla gerbilli* - 26%, *Xenopsylla conformis* - 8.6%; Among the fleas of the subgenus *Nosopsyllus*, *Nosopsyllus laeviceps*

dominates - 64.2%, *Nosopsyllus turkmenicus* made up 22.5%, less represented are *Nosopsyllus trispinus* - 8.3% and *tersus* - 4.6%; fleas of the genus *Coptopsylla* are represented by only 2 subgenera, these are *Coptopsylla lamellifer* - 85.4% and *Coptopsylla bairamaliensis* - 14.5%; followed by the genus *Mesopsylla*, represented by *Mesopsylla tushkan* - 43%, *Mesopsylla hebes* - 33.3% and *Mesopsylla lenis* - 23.7%; The last in the gradation under consideration were fleas of the genus *Stenoponia*, represented by the dominance of the subgenus *Stenoponia vlasovi* - 95% and *Stenoponia conspecta* - 5%.

Fig. 6. Flea dominance indices by territory.

The occurrence in collections is noted by the following features, applicable to the analyzed territories: in Kyzylkum Desert, the least common, including in recent years, were *Xenopsilla skrjabini*, *Xenopsilla Nuttali* and *Paradoxopsylla teretifrons*, the genus *Mesopsylla* and the subgenera *Stenoponia conspekta*, *Nosopsyllus tesquorum* and *Neopsylla setosa* were not found at all; The territories of the Ustyurt biotopes are distinguished by the following: the least common were *Xenopsilla hirtipes*, *Xenopsilla Nuttali*, *Paradoxopsylla teretifrons*, *Stenoponia conspecta* and *Nosopsyllus tesquorum*, *Mesopsylla hebes* and *Nosopsyllus tesquorum* were not found in the collections of recent years, and the ectoparasites *Coptopsylla olgae* and *Rostropsylla daca* were not found in the collections. It is worth noting the isolated appearance of specimens in collections in territories where they were previously not found or extremely rare: for the Kyzylkum focus, these are fleas of the subgenus *Xenopsilla skrjabini* (the most numerous for the Ustyurt territory), *Nosopsyllus trispinus* (one of the dominant species of Ustyurt); for the Ustyurt focus this is *Xenopsilla hirtipes* (the highest dominance index in Kyzylkum).

The analysis of the tick composition of the collections territorially provided the following data: the dominant or vectorial nature with respect to ticks was established, as before, for the order *Ixodida*, the dominant family was *Ixodidae*. In the Kyzylkum Desert, the distribution by genera is

as follows: genus *Hyalomma* (genus Ixodidae order Ixodida) - 92.1%; genus), genus *Ornithodoros* (family *Argasidae* order Ixodida) - 8.7%, genus *Ixodes* (subfamily *Ixodinae*) - 5%, genus *Haemaphysalis* (*Ixodidae*) - 0.35%. The territory of Ustyurt is noted in the following ratio: *Hyalomma* - 48.8%; *Ornithodoros* - 33%; *Haemaphysalis* – 25.9%, *Rhipicephalus* – 6.3%, and *Ixodes* – 1.2%. Prevalence indices correlate with dominance indices. It should be noted that in the Kyzylkum Desert during the analyzed period, *Haemaphysalis* ticks were encountered only once, while *Rhipicephalus* ticks were not encountered at all. In the Ustyurt Desert, *Ixodes* ticks were encountered once at the beginning of observations, with a total of 20 specimens.

Fig. 7. 1-dynamics of the external temperature in June at the Zhaslyk weather station (Ustyurt); 2-dynamics of the external temperature in December at the Zhaslyk weather station; 3-dynamics of the external temperature in June at the Tamdybulak weather station (Kyzylkum); 4-dynamics of the external temperature in December at the Tamdybulak weather station [9].

Fig. 8. 1-Dynamics of external humidity indicators in June at the Zhaslyk weather station (Ustyurt); 2-Dynamics of external humidity indicators in December at the Zhaslyk weather station [9];

Considering the dynamics of the psychrothermal trend in the analyzed territory in the period from 1974 to 2025, it is objectively observed that there is a high level of pressure from these indicators on the biota of all deserts of Uzbekistan, especially in the Kyzylkum and Ustyurt deserts, which is expressed as a result in climate change towards accelerating and increasing aridization and, as a consequence, negatively affecting the vital signs of rodent populations and their ectoparasites, especially in the last decade of observations.

Fig. 9. 1-Dynamics of external humidity indicators in June at the Tamdytruba weather station (Kyzylkum); 2-Dynamics of external humidity indicators in December at the Tamdytruba weather station [9];

Attempts are being made to mitigate these circumstances in the form of saxaul plantings - in 2018, a program [10] of afforestation in the dried-up part of the Aral Sea [13] was launched, and today, out of 2.9 million hectares of drained areas of the sea, 1.8 million hectares are already covered with saxaul, which locally contributes to some optimization of the situation (positive shifts in the indicators of rodent generation) and the interpenetration of representatives of the Kyzylkum biogeocenoses and the dried bottom of the Aral Sea (the data presented, in particular, on ectoparasites), which, in aggregate, changes the composition of the previously observed composition of desert biotopes and requires systematic in-depth study on an ongoing basis, in view of, among other things, monitoring the state of natural desert plague foci.

Fig. 10. Cartographic representation of saxaul planting areas on the Aral Sea floor [11].

Conclusion

Summarizing the above, it appears that a decrease in epizootic potential is observed. However, given retrospective data, this conclusion is premature, and the discussion of reducing the intensity of the "pulsation" of these natural autonomous plague foci is controversial, particularly because the problem of the persistence and circulation of the plague microbe remains open [12, 14]. The author expresses gratitude to the entire writing team for their methodological and practical assistance in writing this article. The authors confirm that they have no conflicts of financial or non-financial interest related to the writing of this article.

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